

THE PROBLEM OF FORMATION OF LANGUAGE COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Abstract. *The article describes the importance of developing the participation skills of primary school students. This is due to the fact that the main result of the educational process in primary school depends on how much competence the student has mastered. A student with developed linguistic and cultural competencies delves into the grammatical structure of the Kazakh language, understands the patterns of use of certain grammatical rules in speech, and studies the mechanism of sentence construction. Without this competence, undocumented theoretical skills will turn into superficial training. To a certain extent, the linguistic competence of students is a necessary condition for the organization of their skills and language communication skills. Correctly formed linguacultural competencies help students deeply understand the phonetic, lexical and grammatical phenomena being studied, understand the mechanism of word formation, the rules of correct spelling, the presence of any types of speech related to language, and syntactic structures etc. helps to understand. Because it helps to understand and comprehend the linguistic facts being studied, and accelerates the practical acquisition of associations.*

Keywords: *formation of participation competence, competence, participation competence of primary school students*

Introduction

The problem of formation of language competence of primary school students in modern scientific research in the field of linguo didactics shows many theoretical and practical problems including necessary to create a new content for learning language skills of children. The main purpose of today's primary school is to create all the conditions for the student to realize their personal potential, to reveal the individuality of the child, to help him to identify, develop and stabilize. At school, every child should be formed as a unique individual. Discovering the individuality of each child in the learning process should organize personality-oriented education at school. For this purpose, special attention is paid to new strategies that promote mutual understanding, successful communication of students, the successful solution of problems of communicative and cultural significance. Psychologists, on the other hand, begin research when the speaker has a clear idea of what he is going to say. As a result, only the process of grammatical and lexical implementation of the word from the imaginary sketch is studied. However, the problem of studying a phenomenon that occurs earlier in a logical order is rarely raised. A student should know what to say through his knowledge and experience in language communication in order to know how to express one's thoughts and opinions. According to the results of recent research by journalists and methodologists, the majority of primary school students have a poor

vocabulary, inability to compose phrases, sentences and texts, which they can not say [or write] on a regular basis. The main reason of the lack of knowledge of students is due to the lack of language and cultural competence, some researchers believe that language lessons in schools are not conducted on the level[1,2].

The concept of "competence" is considered widely in the learning process . Also, the concept of "competence" was first introduced by psychologist R.White in 1959 and is reflected in his book which is called «Motivation reconsidered: The concept of competence». Scientist recognized the term competent (French) - competent, competents (Latin) - relevant, capable, competence (English) - ability (competence) [3,35]. Besides, there have been published more than 300 works on competence over the last 60 years. Although, there were differences in views of scientists as well as they believed that competence is the result of learning. The concept of "competence" appeared in the world of labor and industrial enterprises. The term "key competence" was appeared in the project of the Council of Europe "Secondary Education in Europe" in 1992 . The main goal of this project was to analyze the purpose and content of education in the countries of European Union and assessing mechanisms of student achievements level.

The International Labor Organization has included the concept of "key competencies" in the qualification requirements for specialists who pass the system of postgraduate education and advanced training of management specialists. Key competencies in the training of specialists in vocational schools have been expressed since the 1990s.

Competent philosophical interpretation demonstrates the way to innovations and related to human cognition and practice, as well as determining the educational requirements for the pedagogical situation in each classroom.

We have analyzed the works of scientists on the issue of competence and decided to divide it into three main stages in order to understand the essence and meaning of linguistic and cultural competence in our work.

The first stage is the period when the concept of competence is introduced into the scientific community and it differs from the skills and competencies. The language was first identified and introduced by N.Chomsky into the scientific community during this period. N.Chomsky considered the competence that it is a usage of language in practice right [4,79].

According to N.Chomsky, the competence is considered "the correct application of the laws and rules of language in practice in different situations", later he formed the concept of "competence" in the application of human knowledge, skills in practice and in terms of their own views and opinions [4]. Dell Hymes first defined the term "communicative competence" continuing the opinion of N. Chomsky. Formation of the concept of "competence" closely associated with the name of John Raven. John Raven defined the term "competence" as the competence which consists of many independent components" in his book "Competence in Modern Society", in 1984. Several components consist of the form of cognitive zone and motivational zone [5]. The scientist explained the concept of "competence" in terms of "motivational abilities". J.Raven identified 37 types of competencies and explained in details. The concept of the scientist described the formation of the concept and became the subject of scientific research such as psychology, pedagogy, socialization, sociology, etc.[6], [7], [8], [9].

The second stage is considered as the end result of the competence training process. It is believed that the concept of "competence" in the learning process is used to solve the problem of

knowledge and experience, skills and abilities of students. At this stage, the basic social principles and principles of competence were considered. Areas such as information competence, cognitive competence, competence to learn information have developed and entered the scientific community [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16]. Competencies are expressed as subject (interdisciplinary, etc.) and key competencies. The Council of Europe has identified five groups of key competencies, with special emphasis on them.

1) Political and social competencies: the ability to take responsibility, participate in joint decision-making, non-violent conflict resolution, participation in and improvement of democratic institutions.

2) Competencies related to the ability to live in a multicultural society: to prevent the birth and spread of racism and xenophobia, education should equip young people with intercultural competencies such as understanding differences, respect for each other, ability to live with people of other cultures and religions.

3) Competences related to the acquisition of oral and written forms of communication, the importance of the latter at work and in public life is so great that a person who does not master it is at risk of exclusion from society. This group includes knowledge of several languages that are becoming increasingly important today.

4) Competences related to the use and recognition of public information, mastering new technology, understanding its usage, identifying its strengths and weaknesses, critical approach to information and advertising in media.

5) Lifelong learning ability considered as a basis for continuing education and training, as well as personal and social life [17], [18], [19], [20].

The third stage of the competence is recognized in terms of human abilities, and competencies include human motivation. Competences are recognized for individual abilities and ways to develop them are identified. New terms appeared during this period, such as "student competence", "formation of student competence", "interrelation of competencies in the learning process", "social significance of competencies". The description of the key competencies system developed at Cambridge and Oxford University states that competencies develop in the implementation of various activities, such as academic and professional activities.

The main goals and objectives of education in the 21st century is defined on the documents of UNESCO, such as, teaching to learn (learning to study); training to work and earn money (study for work, ability to act); life skills (problem-solving skills); to teach to live together (learning to live together).

The following list of key competencies has been compiled as part of the European Secondary Education project:

Research: the ability to benefit from experience; linking and regulating their knowledge; ability to organize independent learning methods; problem solving ability; ability to read independently.

Search: search for various information; ask around; consultation with an expert; obtaining information; work with documents and their classification.

Thinking: organization of interaction of past and present events; critical approach to the development of a particular aspect of society; resistance to insecurity and difficulty; have their own position in the debate and prove their point; understand the importance of the political and

economic environment in which they study and work; assessment of social habits related to health, needs and the environment; be able to appreciate works of art and literature.

Collaborative action: ability to work in a team; decision making; ability to resolve conflicts; negotiation skills, contract preparation and conclusion.

Getting started: joining the project; responsibility; join and contribute to a group or team; ability to organize their work; work with computers and modeling devices.

Adaptation: ability to use new information and communication technologies; to withstand difficulties; ability to make new decisions.

This list is approved as a working document in defining key competencies. Therefore, we do not consider the given list as a result of key competencies.

The main outcome of the primary school learning process depends on how competent a student is. The student, who has developed communicative competencies, knows the grammatical structure of the English language, understands the laws of application of certain grammatical rules in speech, masters the mechanism of sentence formation. And the undocumented shafts of theoretical supplementation without competence become superficial training. To a certain extent, the language competencies of students are a necessary condition for the organization of their language communication skills and competencies. Properly formed linguistic and cultural competencies help students to gain a deeper understanding of the phonetic, lexical, grammatical phenomena studied, to understand the mechanism of word formation, the rules of correct spelling, the presence of any forms of linguistic communication, syntactic structures, etc. Because, it helps to gain a deeper understanding of the linguistic facts under study and accelerates the practical acquisition of communication. This is a necessary condition for a conscious practical form of such a method of practical teaching of language theory. The teaching of language theory is carried out in accordance with the usual habits of language communication as a result of equipping students with clear knowledge, communication skills and competencies. Hence, a necessity to determine the amount and content of theoretical information provided to students. All linguistic terms declared as (theory (theoretical material), as well as grammatical definitions, rules, concepts, interlinguistic and interlinguistic comparisons, explanations of linguistic phenomena, grammatical models, tables related to the communicative method of teaching etc. We understand all those who try to consciously master the language materials being taught). The content of theoretical materials determines the communicative purpose of teaching: language theory should help students to regulate speech skills, to master the language as a system. In our opinion, “competence” is a general ability based on knowledge, experience, values and abilities accumulated during training. Competence does not include knowledge or skills, their combination, the practical application of knowledge. The acquisition of competencies in primary school depends on the student's activity. The formation of the language and cultural competence of students is of a practical nature and is based on the functional literacy of the student, as well as as a result of the personal development of the subject of the student's activity.

Assimilation of cognitive information by students in the learning process and the solution of the problem are recognized as language competence. Because, a person lives in a society and interacts with other people. A child develops on the basis of relationships. A child's attendance at kindergarten, school, vocational training, and life itself are based on communication skills. The delivery, reception, collection, modification, storage and use of information are communicative tools.

Modern dictionaries give different term definitions for the concept “culture.” In particular:

- culture - a set of achievements and creativity of a particular people;
- culture - the activities and peculiarities of human society in a particular historical space (Paleolithic culture, Cretan-Mycenaean culture, Kazakh culture, etc.);
- culture - the level of maturity of a particular area of human activity (speech culture, labor culture, legal culture, etc.).

The progressive phenomenon, which usually has to be in the literary language, manifests itself at a certain stage of its development. The goal of our specialists is to develop the language. This should be the main principle of normalization. If there is a stylistic and other meaning in that deviation, we call it a deviation. We are not against deviations from the norm, but only unreasonable deviations. Therefore, the formation of language and cultural competencies of primary school students is to teach them to follow the language norms, to speak according to the language norms.

Summing up the chapter, we draw the following conclusions:

1. In our opinion, "competence" is a general ability based on the knowledge, experience, values and aptitudes accumulated during training. Competence does not belong to knowledge or skills, they are a combination of knowledge and practical application of knowledge.

2. The formation of linguistic and cultural competence of students has an action character and is based on the functional literacy of the student, as well as the result of the personal development of the subject of the student's activity.

3. The teaching of language theory is carried out in accordance with the usual habits of language communication as a result of equipping students with clear knowledge, communication skills and competencies. Hence, necessity is to determine the amount and content of theoretical information provided to students.

4. Formation of linguistic and cultural competence of primary school students is to teach children to maintain the purity of language, to teach the correct use of English language norms, to limit the use of jargon, rude words in the language.

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